

Positive emotions for inciting behavior - Playing with paintings to enhance museum experiences

Hung-Chu Shih¹
hey311511@gmail.com

JungKyoon Yoon¹
j.yoon@tudelft.nl

Arnold P.O.S. Vermeeren¹
a.p.o.s.vermeeren@tudelft.nl

¹Delft University of
Technology, the
Netherlands

Abstract In this paper we propose a new design approach in which positive emotional experiences are used to incite desirable behaviors, based on the insight that specific experiences can motivate particular behaviors. In the approach, designers first identify users' concerns and expectations and deduce from those the psychological needs that underlie them. Positive emotions are then sought that match the identified psychological needs. The positive emotions with their related thought-action tendencies then inspire the designer to formulate design intentions in terms of experiences and behaviors to target for, aimed at guiding the design process. The approach was developed for, and applied to a design case for the Mauritshuis, a museum for classical art in the Hague, the Netherlands. An app was developed for engaging a new target group of young adult travelers: to enhance their art appreciation and to motivate them to explore the local Dutch culture. We explain the various phases including user studies, generating ideas and testing designs, and discuss our experiences with applying this approach.

Keywords *Museum experience, Design for emotions, Positive emotions, Persuasive design, Design for behavioral change*

Introduction

In the field of persuasive technology design research many approaches have been proposed to support designers in influencing the user's behavior through designs that evoke specific experiences. For example, in gamification approaches, game elements such as challenge are used for motivating users to perform particular behaviors (e.g., Blohm & Leimeister, 2013). More in general, Fogg's Behavior Model (2009), explains that people perform specific behaviors if three factors occur at the same time, namely if they: (1) have sufficient motivation, (2) have the ability to perform, and (3) are triggered to show the behavior. One of the insights from Fogg's model with respect to user experience is that people can be motivated to perform the behavior if it provides them with positive emotional experiences, such as pleasure, hope or social acceptance (or their negative counterparts).

In this paper, we focus on the role of positive emotions in influencing user behavior. According to Frijda (2007) emotions differ in terms of their impact on people's perceptions, thoughts and behaviors. For instance, amusement stimulates a person to play socially and share the joviality (Gervais & Wilson, 2005) and courage stimulates to be persistent and continue a certain behavior in the face of a setback. It has been found that people can experience a wide variety of positive emotions when interacting with products, such as pride, relief, desire, and anticipation (Desmet 2008; 2012), and different positive emotions may trigger different user behaviors. A product that evokes surprise draws a person's attention and makes itself more recognizable (Ludden, Schifferstein & Hekkert,

2008), whereas a product that evokes fascination stimulates the user to explore its features and functions (Yoon, Desmet & van der Helm, 2012). These previous studies give insights into the behavioral effects of positive emotions on human-product interactions, but they tend to focus on one or two positive emotions in isolation and do not explain how differentiated positive emotions can be used to deliberately motivate particular behaviors.

In the present paper, we explore a new approach to designing for nuanced positive emotions based on Fogg's (2009) claim that experiences can motivate particular behaviors. We will illustrate and reflect on the approach through a design case that focuses on creating an engaging museum experience for young adult travelers, aimed at improving their art appreciation and their exploration of the local culture.

We first review the relationship between positive emotions and behaviors that served as a theoretical basis of the design approach. Next, we will report our analysis of the behavior of young adult travelers in terms of underlying (abstract) psychological needs, and we will discuss how these led to multiple positive emotions as design targets for inducing favorable behaviors that facilitate an engaging museum experience.

Positive emotions and behavior

The positive impact of pleasure on behavior has been proven in various studies (e.g., Chitturi, 2009; Mugge, Schoormans, & Schifferstein, 2005; Tractinsky, Katz, & Ikar, 2000) and design researchers gave attention to

how design can facilitate positive emotional experiences. Various design approaches and frameworks have been proposed to support designers in their attempts to generate pleasurable experiences (e.g. Jordan, 2000; Norman, 2004). However, these approaches tend to deal with generalized pleasure or a small set of positive emotions, and do not explicitly explain their effects on behavior.

The reason for this may be that contrary to negative emotions, differences between positive emotions experienced in human-product interactions are subtle (Desmet, 2002; Laurans, Desmet, & Hekkert, 2012) and are not seen as directly causing behavior that is readily observable (Fredrickson & Cohn, 2008). Although all distinct emotions always come along with a particular action tendency that influences people's inclinations to behave in a certain manner (Frijda, 2007), action tendencies for positive emotions are less obvious than those for negative ones. For instance, while fear immediately makes us run away and anger makes us oppose, contentment or admiration do not spark such immediate behavior. Fredrickson (1998) proposed the term 'thought-action tendency' to accommodate the characteristics of positive emotions since unlike negative emotions, some positive emotions, e.g. hope and satisfaction, do not stimulate immediate changes in physical action, but primarily in cognitive activity, influencing physical activity afterwards.

Recently, various studies have been published that explored behavioral effects of distinct positive emotions. For example, Fredrickson (2013) compared ten different positive emotions in terms of their impact on behavior; contentment stimulates an urge to savor life circumstances and recent successes (1998), and hope stimulates an urge to commit to the activity at hand (Lazarus, 1991). Since each of these positive emotions involves different thought-action tendencies, they are likely to result in different behaviors in a direct or indirect way (Fredrickson, 2013). In line with this, we propose that understanding the various relationships between emotions and thought-action tendencies can be put to use for purposefully influencing a user's behavior. For example, imagine the task of designing a playful product that will make users jump and look over a wall that is higher than themselves and have a positive emotional experience while doing so. If a designer generates ideas for the positive emotion of surprise the resulting solutions will be different from those of designing for confidence. Design for surprise may, for example, lead to ideas about surprising things that can be seen on the other side of the wall, whilst design for confidence may lead to ideas for challenging users to ever jump higher to have a better look at what is on the other side.

The advantage of considering particular positive emotions is that, as discussed in Yoon, Pohlmeier, & Desmet (2014) and Desmet (2012), it enables designers to clarify their design intentions in terms of emotional impact upfront in the design process, rather than as an afterthought. Presumably this can increase the effectiveness of the design process and its outcomes.

The above studies by Yoon, Pohlmeier, & Desmet (2014) and Desmet (2012) not only demonstrated the benefits of designing for particular positive emotions they also provided insights into design strategies for evoking specific emotions. However, these studies tend to solely focus on emotional experiences, not necessarily taking their implications on users' behaviors into account.

In the following sections we will discuss a design case in which we reflected on the design process, and in which we explored how particular behaviors can be incited by means of positive emotions.

Design case

Background

In our design case we explore to what extent, in line with the theories of Fogg (2009) and Frijda (2007), positive emotional experience can facilitate desired behaviors in a physical context. We collaborated with the museum "the Mauritshuis" and design consultancy "Kiss the Frog" to create an engaging museum experience that provides visitors of the Mauritshuis with positive emotional experiences and influences their behaviors.

The Mauritshuis is a classical art museum, in the center of The Hague, the Netherlands, mainly exhibiting paintings from the Dutch Golden Age period (17th century), including Rembrandt and Vermeer. A study by the Dutch Museum Association (2010) showed that the Dutch museum sector would meet at least three challenges in the near future: cuts in subsidies, an increase of the number of international tourists and the rise of the digital generation. These challenges motivated the Mauritshuis to look for new potential visitors; one of these is the young adult traveler. The project goal was to design for a product-service system that enhances the art appreciation of young adult travelers and motivates them to explore the local culture.

Design approach

The design process began by investigating the current museum experiences of young adult travelers and explored positive emotions from their previous experiences as inspiration for a new engaging museum experience. To help the designers to think outside of the box when exploring possibilities, we adopted an approach similar to that of Hekkert & van Dijk (2011), proposing designers to explore desirable interactions with the product by defining interaction qualities upfront, in the form of multifaceted experiences. The term 'interaction qualities' refers to characteristics of a user's experience of interacting with a product or a service (Hekkert & van Dijk, 2011; Löwgren, 2009).

We first focused on current behaviors along with a visitor's related expectations and concerns, for example the behavior of talking to a companion with the expectation of sharing one's feeling about a painting with others. We then translated these expectations and concerns into psychological needs, for example interpreting the desire of sharing feelings with someone as fulfilling the psychological need of

Figure 1. The framework of the design process.

relatedness (Sheldon et al., 2001). The subsequent step in our design was based on the research of Hassenzahl, Diefenbach and Göritz (2010), which indicates the relation between the fulfillment of psychological needs and positive affects, and the research of Vermeeren et al. (2014) which suggests that experiencing a need may set people to action. Using the abstract definition of the desired need fulfillment, we explored the possible positive emotions that could contribute to an engaging museum experience and of which the thought-action tendencies would facilitate favorable behaviors (Figure 1 depicts our design approach).

Identifying concerns and expectations of the Mauritshuis visitors

The design process started with observing behaviors of young adult travelers in the Mauritshuis, and with identifying their expectations and concerns in relation to the Mauritshuis. The museum experience of young adult travelers can be seen as part of their travel experience. The travel purpose of young adult travelers possibly influences their expectations and concerns in relation to the museum. Therefore, we conducted two user studies to gain a better understanding of desired museum experiences of young adult travelers. The first study was conducted in the form of observations of, and interviews with 16 young adult visitors in the Mauritshuis. The second study consisted of a contextmapping workshop (Sleeswijk Visser et al., 2005) with seven young adult travelers, to better

understand their travel focuses and the association between the travel focuses and museum experiences during the trip (Figure 2). The interviews and discussions in both studies were audio recorded.

Results

The collected data from both studies were transcribed, and interesting quotes were then clustered into groups of expectations and concerns in relation to behaviors; for example the quote, *“I was wandering around trying to find interesting details of the paintings”*, referring to the behavior of looking into the details of the painting, was motivated by the expectation to discover interesting details from the painting. Thus, based on the observations, interviews and workshops, we assessed how certain expectations and concerns of the young adult travelers had led to their behaviors as observed in the museum,

In general, the behaviors of the participants could be clustered into four categories: (1) interacting with paintings, (2) interacting with other visitors, (3) interacting with the museum environment and (4) interacting with people who were not in the museum. For example, the category of “interacting with paintings” included looking into the details of the painting, listening to the audio guide, looking for the famous paintings and taking photos of or with paintings.

From the user research, we could understand that

Figure 2. The photos of the contextmapping workshop.

certain motivations resulted in particular behaviors, but we still did not know which psychological needs had triggered the particular motivations; for example, what is the psychological need behind the behavior of exploring the details of a painting? To deal with this, we used Sheldon et al.'s candidate psychological needs (2001) to make inferences of which latent needs could have been at the basis of the particular observed behaviors.

Identifying psychological needs

Sheldon et al. (2001) proposed that there are ten psychological needs that contribute to satisfying experiences and eventually to personal thriving. We clustered the identified behaviors of the young adult travelers according to Sheldon et al.'s psychological needs; for example, the behavior of exploring the paintings was considered to be related to fulfilling the psychological need of pleasure stimulation. Table 1 shows some examples of the data.

Determining the intended emotional experiences to design for

After identifying the psychological needs of young adult travelers in the Mauritshuis, we determined positive emotions that could be associated with those psychological needs. We adopted the 25 positive emotions from the typology of positive emotions proposed by Desmet (2012) and clustered them into six psychological needs we had identified for the new museum experience. For example, one of the psychological needs of young adult travelers was pleasure-stimulation. Related positive emotions could be fascination, inspiration, enchantment, joy, amusement, surprise, energetic, lust and anticipation. The thought-action tendencies of each positive emotion may then give designers inspiration for designing new museum experiences that would incite particular behaviors for fulfilling the related psychological needs. For example, the thought-action tendency of amusement could motivate young adult travelers to play socially or share the joviality, fulfilling the need of relatedness, while the thought-action tendency of pride may encourage them to reward themselves, show off, or persevere, fulfilling the need of self-actualization.

As shown above, we found that each psychological need can be related to several positive emotions. Different thought-action tendencies of one particular positive emotion (for example, fascination and enchantment) can be combined to stimulate creativity

in coming up with design concepts, whilst designing for two positive emotions at the same time may (but not necessarily does) lead to conflicting situations. For example, design for relaxation and excitement cannot be achieved at the same time. Thus, we created a long list of potential positive emotions to possibly design for, and at this point needed to determine which positive emotions to target at for the new museum experience in the Mauritshuis.

The Mauritshuis had indicated that it is part of their mission to provide visitors with a place for casual learning, social sharing, art appreciation and self-growth. Thus, we decided to particularly look into the psychological needs of competence, relatedness, pleasure-stimulation, and self-actualization, and selected a set of related positive emotions that we considered important, resulting in the five design intentions:

1. Competence: Young adult travelers should feel active/interested to gain new knowledge about the painting. The thought-action tendency of anticipation, joy, fascination and inspiration can trigger the curiosity of young adult travelers about the story behind the painting.
2. Relatedness: Young adult travelers should enjoy the social bounding with others. The thought-action tendency of amusement and joy can encourage young adult travelers to interact with others.
3. Pleasure-stimulation: Young adult travelers should be motivated to look into the details of the painting. The thought-action tendency of fascination, surprise and enchantment can facilitate young adult travelers to explore the painting.
4. Pleasure-stimulation: Young adult travelers should enjoy the cozy atmosphere in the museum. The thought-action tendency of joy and enchantment can facilitate young adult travelers to be absorbed in the museum visiting event.
5. Self-actualization: The exhibition should be meaningful to young adult travelers. The thought-action tendency of pride and satisfaction can encourage young adult travelers to embrace art and culture and can make them feel that they have achieved something meaningful in their lives.

In conclusion, there would be nine positive emotions involved in the engaging museum experience: anticipation, fascination, inspiration, enchantment,

Table 1. Examples of the psychological needs associated with the identified behaviors, expectations, and concerns.

Behavior	Expectation/ Concern	Candidate Psychological Needs
Listen to the audio of the paintings	To learn the meaning / knowledge of the paintings	Competence
Look for famous paintings	Not to miss any good / famous paintings	Security
Appreciate the interior and the view outdoor	Enjoy the atmosphere in the museum	Pleasure-stimulation
Buy the souvenirs	To refresh the exhibition later	Self-actualization-meaning
Share the feelings of the paintings with others	To build the connection with others in the museum	Relatedness
Post the photos taken in the museum online	To show off the unique experience to friends	Popularity-influence
...

Figure 3. Examples of the ideas inspired by positive emotions: surprise (left) and inspiration (right).

amusement, surprise, pride, joy and satisfaction. The thought-action tendencies of these nine positive emotions would form the interaction qualities of the new museum experience and would be used as the source of inspiration for developing concepts.

Developing the concept to incite the behaviors *Ideation session with positive emotions*

We conducted an ideation session that focused on generating ideas inspired by positive emotions that could be related to museum engagement for young adult travelers. Five Industrial Design students from TU Delft joined the session. The session consisted of three parts explained as follow.

Participants first gained an understanding of the target group (part 1), and then they started brainstorming about museum experiences, inspired by positive emotions (part 2). For part 2 we used positive emotional granularity cards (Yoon, Desmet, & Pohlmeier, 2013) each of which contains an explanation of a particular emotion. Designers read the cards and wrote down ideas based on those particular emotions, in the form of either concrete objects or abstract experiences (for example, amazing nature or eye contact for the emotion “enchantment”, respectively). After that, participants again tried to come up with new ideas, this time based on the ideas that others had written down in the previous round.

In the third part of the session, we asked the designers to again generate ideas related to positive emotions, however, now also in response to each of the five design intentions (e.g. ideas for the positive emotions “amusement” and “joy” in response to the design intention “young adult travelers should enjoy the social bounding with others”).

Brainstorming based on the positive emotions led to a variety of ideas. For example, inspired by the emotion ‘surprise’ and its related thought-action tendency of ‘being attentive’ one designer came up with the idea of “Finding funny details in a painting”; and ‘fascination’ led to the idea “comparing the old subject in the painting with what it looks now in the real world” (Figure 3).

We evaluated the generated ideas taking the design intentions as criteria. The evaluation led to the selection of two ideas. One was about an app with a ‘find the differences’ game that would encourage

young adult travelers to explore the beauty of paintings and arouse their interests to learn the story of the paintings. The stories of the paintings would include knowledge about classical arts as well as about Dutch culture. This idea aimed at inciting the behavior of looking into the paintings, listening to audio fragments telling stories about them and talking to their companions in the museum.

The other idea was to provide young adult travelers with a customized museum tour through an app that guides them to explore the topic of the paintings they are interested in. Topics included knowledge about art, Dutch history and cultural trivia. This app aimed at inciting the behavior of listening to audio fragments and sharing their feeling with friends.

The two ideas were developed into two conceptual designs for museum experiences. The museum experiences included young adult travelers experiences before, as well as during the visit to an exhibition and after it. For example, one museum experience enabled young adult travelers to watch an animation about the background of the exhibition before the museum tour started, and allowed them to play the ‘find the differences’ game during the tour and create a personal souvenir after finishing the tour.

Evaluating and improving the generated concepts

A user test session was conducted to evaluate to what extent the two museum experiences could engage young adult travelers in the museum and incite the desired behaviors (Figure 4). It was conducted with seven participants who were invited to participate in role-playing the use of the conceptual designs in a simulated museum environment with paper prototypes. During the test participants’ actions were observed and participants were provided with simulated responses similar to those they would get in reality (e.g., a researcher would manually start an audio fragment). Both designs evoked much of the desired behaviors. However, in the interviews afterwards, they indicated that the ‘find the differences’ game better engaged them for three reasons: (1) it encouraged them to focus on paintings to discover details in it, (2) it enabled them to interact with the paintings in a fun and dynamic way; (3) they liked the idea that the story told in the audio fragments was not only about the artwork itself, but also about information that was closer to their own lives (i.e., Dutch cultural trivia).

Figure 4. Photos of the user test.

The result of the user test showed the potential of the ‘find the differences’ game to engage young adult travelers. We decided to further develop it, and to include some successful elements of the other game concept.

Design of the treasure hunting app

The final design is a treasure hunting app that also contains the function of giving travel tips to the young adult travelers for exploring the Hague (Figure 5). A short movie when starting the app briefly introduces the treasure hunting game. Visitors then select a room to go to. When entering the room they engage in a ‘find the painting’ game based on hints. For example a hint such as ‘light and shadow’ may refer to Ruben’s painting ‘Old Woman and Boy with Candles’. Having found the painting, the app would depict it, but in the depicted painting a few details would be different from the real painting. The player of the game can indicate in the app, the location of the difference and would then be provided with the opportunity of listening to an audio fragment about or related to that detail, narrated by a young adult, local to the city of The Hague.

Typically in the audio fragments a story starts by explaining the painting and the depicted aspects of traditional Dutch culture, and then connects the story to modern Dutch culture. After having identified five ‘treasures’ (i.e., stories related to identified differences), travel tips related to the modern Dutch culture topics will be unlocked. For example, in the app version of the painting ‘Still Life with Cheeses,

Almonds and Pretzels’ the color of the beer bottle would be changed from brown to green, referring to the color of the modern Dutch beer brand Heineken, and one of the breads would be changed into a bread roll with a Dutch ‘kroket’ (popular meat snack) with the travel tip explaining where to get such a snack.

Evaluating the app

We evaluated the app to see whether the final design evoked the desired interaction qualities and incited the particular behaviors. The test was done in the Mauritshuis. Nine young adult travelers participated in the test, using a partly functional prototype while visiting the exhibition. The prototype allowed playing the game, but was limited to five treasures (instead of fifteen in the real design), and participants had to search for them in a pre-defined order. Five participants used the prototype individually and four tested it in pairs. We observed the behaviors of the nine young adult travelers while using the prototype, and asked them to share their experiences of interacting with the paintings (Figure 6). Due to the unfamiliarity of the participants to the topic, instead of asking them to answer which positive emotion they had during the session, we asked them to rate aspects of their museum experience related to the design intentions, on scales of one to five, i.e., “To which degree did you feel motivated to explore the painting?” The participants’ interactions with the apps were video-recorded for studying their actual behavior.

Based on the feedback of the young adult travelers in the evaluation session as well as our observations we

Figure 5. The interfaces of the museum app.

Figure 6. The photos of the design evaluation session.

conclude that the young adult travelers showed behaviors that were largely in line with the five design intentions:

1. Young adult travelers were encouraged to actively gain new knowledge.

The app made the participants curious to learn why a painting was different from how it was depicted in the app, and they mentioned that they were motivated to listen to the audio stories. They mentioned that the story about the local culture related to them and that it had increased their interest in understanding the paintings, as well as motivated them to see more paintings and listen to more audio fragments.

2. Social interactions between young adult travelers were triggered in the museum.

By the two pairs of participants the game of interacting with the paintings was seen as an activity that they could do together and that triggered interactions between them. They cooperated to find the paintings with the provided clues and to find the differences between the real painting and the picture in the app. The audio story about the local culture in some cases also triggered conversations between two participants, making them share previous experiences in the city.

3. Young adult travelers were motivated to explore the details of the painting.

The app incited to look for the paintings with the 'treasures' and compare the original painting with the one depicted in the app. Both activities guided them to actively look into the details of paintings. The app changed their behaviors from passively receiving the information to playing with the paintings.

4. Young adult travelers were engaged in the cozy atmosphere of the museum.

The app created an interactive museum experience without interfering with the cozy historic atmosphere in the museum. The participants appreciated the art, had fun with friends and gained new knowledge about Dutch local culture

by using the app. They appreciated that they could play and stop the app anytime they wanted.

5. Young adult travelers had a meaningful experience.

The audio stories about art and local culture and the travel tips were both created by local young adults. These were intended to imitate the experience of meeting new local friends telling them interesting stories about Dutch culture and art. The stories of the paintings and the recommendations in the travel tips from the local young adults facilitated young adult travelers to engage in the museum and in the Netherlands. It enhanced their interest to explore the city, which could make the trip more unique and meaningful

Through the evaluation of the app, we could see that the app has a potential to stimulate young adult travelers to actively learn about the paintings, interact with a companion, and open up to explore local culture even after leaving the museum. However, some usability problems were identified during the test. Prior to implementation of the concept, the flow of the user interface needs to be further refined, so that people will be able to use the app and to engage in the activities stimulated by the design without supplementary instructions.

General discussion

In this paper, we proposed a new approach in which particular positive emotions are used to influence user behavior and demonstrated its application through a design case. We first analyzed the behaviors of users in relation to their expectations and concerns, and inferred what kinds of psychological needs would underlie those. Based on the identified needs and the goal of the project, a set of positive emotions was chosen taking their associated thought-action tendencies into account, which then served as design intentions in the phase of idea generation. At the end, we evaluated the result of our design approach with the prototype of the final design.

During the design process, we encountered some challenges of clustering expectations into the needs; some expectations appeared to be difficult to relate to the exact definitions of the ten psychological needs defined by Sheldon et al. (2001). We therefore slightly

redefined the needs to fit the museum context. For example, instead of defining the competence as “one was successfully completing difficult tasks” (Sheldon et al, 2001), we transformed the definition to “one feels capable of completing the tasks one chose to perform” for clustering the expectation of gaining new knowledge about the paintings. The redefinition was based on Cognitive Evaluation Theory (Deci & Ryan, 1985) indicating that people experience satisfaction if they fulfill both needs of competence and autonomy for a high level of intrinsic motivation. The broader definition of the competence helped us consider a wider range of positive emotions.

The results of the design evaluation indicated that the final design of the museum app led young adult travelers to perform the target behaviors. However, the current study comes with some limitations. Although we initially intended to see if the app could actually evoke the targeted positive emotions, the questionnaire used in the test only dealt with the possible effects of the app on the participants’ behaviors inside the museum. Measuring positive emotions at a detailed level was not possible, due to a lack of design support for that. Moreover, since the prototype was only partly functional, we could not observe the effects of the app on the participants’ behaviors after their museum visit (i.e., in terms of engaging with the local culture) and we had to rely on their self-reported opinions and intentions for that. With a more sophisticated prototype, the behavioral effects could have been examined.

Conclusion

This paper explores a new design approach based on Fogg’s (2009) claim that experiences can motivate particular behaviors. We assume that the approach provides a structure for influencing user behavior through emotions as it shows the process of conceiving favorable behaviors and positive emotions in a systematic way. Future case studies that involve different design contexts (e.g., hospitals and train stations) will allow us to further refine the proposed approach. Furthermore, in the paper we address positive emotions enhancing the motivation to perform behavioral change; however, ability and trigger, the other two factors that influence behavioral change in Fogg’s theory, could be taken into account in the future study to improve the approach.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank Geert-Jan Borgstein of The Mauritshuis and Ronald Theunissen of Kiss the Frog for providing us with the opportunity to conduct this study, and the participants in the studies for their participation.

References

Blohm, I., & Leimeister, J. M. (2013). Gamification: Design of IT-Based Enhancing Services for Motivational Support and Behavioral Change. *Business Information System & Engineering (BISE)*, 5(4), 275-278, DOI:10.1007/s12599-013-0273-5.

BJ Fogg. 2009. A behavior model for persuasive design. In Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Persuasive Technology (Persuasive ‘09). ACM, New York, NY, USA, , Article 40. DOI=10.1145/1541948.1541999

Chitturi, R. (2009). Emotions by design: A consumer perspective. *International Journal of Design*, 3(2), 7–17.

Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (1985). *Intrinsic motivation and self-determination in human behavior*. New York: Plenum.

Desmet, P. M. A. (2002). *Designing emotions. Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering*. Delft, the Netherlands: Delft University of Technology.

Desmet, P.M.A. (2003). Measuring emotion; development and application of an instrument to measure emotional responses to products. In: M.A. Blythe, A.F. Monk, K. Overbeeke, & P.C. Wright (Eds.), *Funology: from usability to enjoyment* (pp. 111-123). Dordrecht: Kluwer Academic Publishers.

Desmet, P. M. A. (2012). Faces of product pleasure: 25 positive emotions in human-product interactions. *International Journal of Design*, 6(2), 1-29.

Desmet, P. M. A., & Schifferstein, H. (2012). Emotion research as input for product design. In J. H. Beckley, K. Lopetcharat, & D. Paredes (Eds.), *Product Innovation Toolbox* (pp. 149–175). John Wiley & Sons.

Fredrickson, B. L. (1998). What Good Are Positive Emotions?, 2(3), 300–319.

Fredrickson, B. L., & Cohn, M. A. (2008). Positive emotions. In M. Lewis, J. M. Haviland-Jones, & L. F. Barrett (Eds.), *Handbook of emotions* (3rd ed., pp. 777–798). New York: Guilford Press.

Fredrickson, B. L. (2013). Positive Emotions Broaden and Build. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 47, 1–53. <http://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-407236-7.00001-2>

Frijda, N. H. (2007). *The Laws of Emotion*. London: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers.

Hekkert, P. & van Dijk, M.B. (2011). *Vision in design: A guidebook for innovators*. Amsterdam: BIS publishers.

Hassenzahl, M., Diefenbach, S., & Göritz, A. (2010). Needs, affect, and interactive products – Facets of user experience. *Interacting with Computers*, 22(5), 353-362. doi:10.1016/j.intcom.2010.04.002

Jordan, P. W. (2000). *Designing Pleasurable Products: An Introduction to the New Human factors*. London: Taylor and Francis.

Laurans, G., Desmet, P. M. A., & Hekkert, P. (2012). Assessing emotion in human–product interaction: an overview of available methods and a new approach. *International Journal of Product Development*, 16(3), 225–242.

Löwgren, J. (2009). Towards an articulation of interaction aesthetics. *New Review of Hypermedia and Multimedia*, 15(2), 129–146.

Ludden, G. D. S., Schifferstein, H. N. J. & Hekkert, P. (2008) Surprise as a design strategy. *Design Issues*, 24(2), pp 28-38.

Mugge, R., Schoormans, J. P. L., & Schifferstein, H. N. J. (2005). Design Strategies to Postpone Consumer' Product Replacement: the Value of a Strong Person-Product Relationship. *The Design Journal*, 8(2), 38–48.

Museumvereniging. (2010). Agenda 2026: Study on the future of the Dutch Museum Sector. Retrieved from <http://www.museumvereniging.nl/Portals/0/6-Publicaties/ Bestanden/Agenda 2026 PDF v4 35231 eng hi-res.pdf>.

Norman, D. A. (2004). *Emotional Design: Why We Love (or Hate) Everyday Things*. New York: Basic Books.

Sheldon, K., Elliot, A., Kim, Y., & Kasser, T. (2001). What is satisfying about satisfying events? Testing 10 candidate psychological needs. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 325-339.

Sleeswijk-Visser F., Stappers P.J., van der Lugt R. & Sanders E. B.-N.(2005) Contextmapping: experiences from practice, *CoDesign*, 1:2,119-149, DOI: 10.1080/15710880500135987

Tractinsky, N., Katz, A., & Ikar, D. (2000). What is beautiful is usable. *Interacting with Computers*, 13, 127–145.

Vermeeren, A.P.O.S., Beusekom, J. van, Rozendaal, M.C. & Giacardi, E. (2014). Design for complex persuasive experiences: Helping parents of hospitalized children take care of themselves. In R Wakkary & S Harrison (Eds.), *DIS 2014, Proceedings of the 2014 conference on designing interactive systems* (pp. 335-344). New York: ACM.

Yoon, J., Desmet, P. M. A., & van der Helm, A. (2012). Design for interest: Exploratory study on a distinct positive emotion in human-product interaction. *International Journal of Design*, 6(2), 67-80.

Yoon, J., Desmet, P. M. A., & Pohlmeier, A. E. (2013). Embodied Typology of Positive Emotions: The Development of a Tool to Facilitate Emotional Granularity in Design (pp. 1195–1206). Presented at the 5th International Congress of International Association of Sciences of Design Research, Tokyo, Japan.

Yoon, J., Pohlmeier, A. E., & Desmet, P. M. A. (2014). Nuances of Emotions in Product Development: Seven Key Opportunities Identified by Design Professionals (pp. 643–652). Presented at the International Design Conference-DESIGN, Dubrovnik, Croatia.